

SPORTS DISCOURSE IN LINGUISTICS

Gavkhar Khaydarova

English teacher at Filology department,
The institute of International School of Finance Technology and Science,
gavharmoon1984@gmail.com
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12576882>

Abstract

This article discusses the role of sports discourse in linguistics. Moreover, it discusses the importance of relying on different disciplines, namely sociology, psychology, and communication studies, in the analysis of sport contexts.

Keywords: discourse, sports discourse, discourse analysis, communication, sports journalists, sports commentators.

In linguistics, "discourse" refers to spoken or written communication that extends beyond individual sentences. It encompasses larger units of language, such as conversations, narratives, speeches, or texts, and examines how these units are structured, how meaning is constructed within them, and how they function in various contexts. Discourse analysis explores the relationships between language, society, and culture, and examines the ways in which language is used to convey meaning, convey social roles and identities, negotiate power dynamics, and construct knowledge and reality. It involves analyzing features such as cohesion, coherence, genre, register, and the organization of discourse, as well as examining the social and cultural contexts in which discourse occurs. Sports discourse in linguistics is a field of study that examines the language used in the context of sports, including communication among athletes, coaches, spectators, commentators, and sports journalists. This interdisciplinary area draws on theories and methods from linguistics, sociology, psychology, and communication studies to analyze various aspects of language in sports contexts.

Discourse in linguistics refers to the organization and creation of language beyond individual sentences, encompassing both spoken and written communication for various purposes. It comprises segments of language larger or smaller than a single sentence but always conveying meaning beyond the sentence level. Discourse extends beyond sentential boundaries and involves any coherent succession of sentences, spoken or written, where successive sentences or utterances are connected. Formalist and functionalist paradigms in linguistics offer differing views on discourse, with the former defining it as language above the sentence or clause, and the latter emphasizing its use in context. Discourse analysis, a rapidly evolving area of linguistics, focuses on

understanding how language users interpret meaning, comprehend texts, engage in conversation, and perceive coherence in connected discourse. Zellig Harris, credited with introducing discourse analysis, viewed discourse as a hierarchical level above morphemes, clauses, and sentences, emphasizing its structural nature. Michael Stubbs highlights the shift from studying sentences in isolation to examining utterances in context, indicating that discourse analysis encompasses any study beyond single sentences, contrived by linguists and out of context. Understanding language in use as discourse entails considering not only linguistic construction but also reference, sense, and force in situational contexts. This approach challenges the notion that discourse is merely sentences writ large and underscores the qualitative differences that emerge beyond the sentence level.

Here are some key points and topics within sports discourse in linguistics:

Language Variation: Language in sports exhibits variation based on factors such as regional dialects, socio-economic backgrounds, and cultural influences. Linguists study how these variations manifest in sports discourse, both on and off the field.

Genre Analysis: Sports discourse includes various genres such as play-by-play commentary, interviews, press conferences, match reports, fan discussions, and social media interactions. Linguists analyze the linguistic features and conventions of each genre to understand how meaning is constructed and conveyed.

Identity and Power: Language in sports reflects and constructs social identities, power dynamics, and hierarchies within the sports community. Linguistic research explores how language is used to negotiate and reinforce identities based on factors like race, gender, nationality, and social class.

Language and Performance: Linguists examine the role of language in shaping athletic performance, including motivational speech, team communication, and coaching strategies. They investigate how linguistic cues influence athletes' mindset, confidence, and decision-making during competition.

Media Discourse: Sports media, including television broadcasts, newspaper articles, and online platforms, play a significant role in shaping public perceptions of sports events and athletes. Linguistic analysis of media discourse explores how language constructs narratives, frames controversies, and influences audience interpretation.

Fan Discourse: Fans engage in a variety of linguistic practices, such as chanting, cheering, and online discussions, to express support for their favorite teams and

players. Linguists study fan discourse to understand the role of language in fan culture, identity formation, and community building.

Multimodality: Sports discourse often involves multimodal communication, combining language with visual elements such as gestures, facial expressions, and body language. Linguistic research examines how verbal and nonverbal cues interact to convey meaning in sports contexts.

Language and Globalization: In an era of globalization, sports serve as a platform for cross-cultural communication and exchange. Linguists investigate how language facilitates interactions among athletes, coaches, and fans from diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds.

Language Policy and Planning: Sports organizations and governing bodies implement language policies and guidelines to regulate communication within the sports community. Linguists study the impact of language policies on inclusivity, accessibility, and linguistic diversity in sports.

Language and Technology: Advances in technology have transformed the way sports are consumed and discussed, with innovations such as live streaming, social media, and data analytics shaping sports discourse. Linguistic research examines how technology influences language use and communication practices in sports.

Overall, sports discourse in linguistics provides valuable insights into the complex interplay between language, culture, and society within the realm of sports. By analyzing linguistic practices in sports contexts, researchers contribute to our understanding of how language functions as a dynamic and multifaceted aspect of human interaction.

Scholars have increasingly turned to discourse analysis as both a theoretical framework and methodological tool. This approach, fundamentally concerned with communicative acts, holds significant importance for the examination of sport media and communication. Despite this, there appears to be a gap in the literature regarding an overarching examination of discourse analysis within the realms of sport, exercise, and physical education studies. To address this gap, we undertook a systematic scoping review, initially identifying 1892 papers from 277 journals spanning the years 2000 to April 2022. Subsequently, we refined our focus to 587 papers specifically employing discourse analysis in the study of sport. Our aim was to delineate prevalent theoretical traditions, explore which sub-disciplines within sport studies embrace discourse analysis, particularly in communication contexts, and elucidate how this approach can contribute to the

methodological and theoretical advancements in the study of media and communication in sport.

Our review revealed a predominant reliance on Foucauldian discourse analysis and critical discourse analysis across various sport disciplines. However, it was noted that discourse analysis is comparatively less common in sport communication journals. To propel the utilization of discourse analysis in our field, we propose several avenues for further exploration. Firstly, we advocate for the adoption of a multimodal approach to discourse analysis, which acknowledges the diverse modes of communication present in sporting contexts. Additionally, we emphasize the integration of technological tools and methodologies within discourse analysis practices, recognizing the increasingly digital nature of contemporary sports media. Finally, we advocate for a shift towards theorizing beyond the confines of dominant approaches, directing attention towards the examination of mediated social interactions within the sporting sphere. Through these suggestions, we envision an enriched understanding of discourse analysis in sport studies and its potential to inform broader discussions within media and communication scholarship.

References:

1. Schirato T. Sports discourse. // Bloomsbury publishing. – 2013. – p.43
2. Rowe D. Sport, Culture and Media: The Unruly Trinity. Second edition. – 2004. – p.108
3. Razhina R.A. The language peculiarities of sport discourse in the national world picture: cognitive and pragmatic approaches//CyberLeninka.-2016. №.1. – P. 98
4. Billings A.C., Brody J. Rauhley J. Digital Media and Sports Discourse: The Role of Twitter in Shaping Fan Interactions. – 2013. P.65
5. Billings A.C. Gender parity in the Olympics.//Journal of Sport and Social Issues. - 1999 23(2)140-170